

Assessment of aqueous extract of *Carica papaya* leaves for inhibitory effects on calcium carbonate scale formation

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ABSTRACT

Calcium carbonates (CaCO₃) are well recognized as one of the most prevalent scale components found in the oil and gas sectors. Calcium carbonate scale frequently accumulates on machinery and parts, producing significant operating issues. Scale inhibitors are the most often used remedies for preventing scale precipitation. In this paper, the potential of a green scale inhibitor developed from paw-paw (*Carica papaya*) leaves was evaluated. Paw-paw leaf water extracts (PLWE) and Pawpaw leaf methanol extract (PLME) were characterized using the Fourier transform infrared, whose result shows that they have more than four absorption band making them complex molecule, with PLWE attributes of surface behaviour, and hydrophilicity while PLME is hydrophobic, hence, PLWE was used for further evaluation. Phytochemical constituents of the pawpaw leaf extract showed the presence of saponin, flavonoids, tannins, amino acids and phenolic compounds, which are the inhibitive agents. Static jar test was employed to evaluate and compare PLWE and a commercial organic scale inhibitor (COSI) scale inhibition performance, with results showing that as the treatment dosage and time of PLWE and COSI increases at 70°C, the scale inhibition rate rises until a threshold is reached. When the treatment dosage of PLWE and COSI is 100ppm at 70°C for 24Hrs, an optimum inhibition rate of 52% and 95% respectively was attained. At higher temperature of 90°C, the optimum inhibition rate of 71% for PLWE was attained at 120 ppm for 24Hrs. Also, the influence of the various dosages of PLWE on the surface phase of the calcium carbonate scales was determined using SEM analyses; it showed loosen structures of scale, altering the morphology of crystals formed, confirming the inhibition mechanism. The use of the Paw-paw leaf water extract in this study as green scale inhibitor has a potential application in inhibiting oilfield calcium carbonate scales.

Keywords: Leave extract, scale inhibition, phytochemicals, paw-paw leaf, calcium carbonate scales

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INTRODUCTION

In the petroleum industry, “scale” refers to solid deposits that accumulate over time, obstructing fluid flow through pipelines, valves, and pumps, resulting in substantial decreases in production rates and equipment damages [1]. Calcium carbonates are prevalent scale-deposit minerals in water treatment facilities in the oil and gas sector, resulting in considerable increase in the production cost. Scaling in the oilfield, refers to the precipitation and buildup of insoluble crystals (salts) resulting from mixing incompatible aqueous phases in oil processing systems [2]. For several years, chemical scale inhibitors have been employed to effectively avoid the formation of mineral scales, including calcite and barite, in oil field production, water heating systems, and circulating refrigeration systems. Some of these inhibitors exhibit minimal biodegradability and are hazardous post-disposal [3,4].

The scale-inhibitor manufacturers and oilfield companies have been compelled to transition to "green scale inhibitors" that are non-toxic, readily biodegradable, and have minimal environmental impact due to the growing environmental concerns of regulatory authorities and discharge restrictions [5,6,7]. Recent studies have highlighted numerous green alternatives for scale inhibition. Zhang *et al.* [8] developed a graft copolymerized cellulose-based inhibitor that achieved 100% efficiency against CaCO₃ scaling. Abu-Bakar *et al.* [9] demonstrated rhamnolipid biosurfactants' effectiveness in suppressing CaCO₃ crystal formation. Huang *et al.* [10] introduced a PESA–IA copolymer that interacted with CaCO₃ crystals to disrupt their growth. Chen *et al.* [11] evaluated oxidized lignosulfonates and confirmed their potential as eco-friendly inhibitors. Review articles by Mazumder [12] and Xu *et al.* [13] consolidated progress in biodegradable inhibitors, emphasizing polymers and plant-based compounds. In this regard, it becomes desirable to assess the effectiveness of some new biodegradable scale inhibitors on calcium carbonate precipitation in oilfields. This study is therefore aimed at developing a green scale inhibitor and evaluating its inhibition performance on calcium carbonate scales formation.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Compositions and preparation of the brine solutions

To assess the inhibitory performance of the scale inhibitor, the brine solutions were prepared as below:

The Calcium-containing brine solution (the cation): NaCl = 33.00g/l, CaCl₂.2H₂O = 12.15g/l, MgCl₂.6H₂O = 3.68g/l.

The Bicarbonate-containing brine solution (the anion): NaCl = 33.00g/l, NaHCO₃ = 7.36g/l, Na₂SO₄ = 0.03g/l.

2.2 Collection and Pretreatment of Paw-paw leaves

Paw-paw leaves were plucked from a Paw-paw tree located in a residential area of Warri, Delta State, Nigeria. They were carefully cleaned with distilled water to remove contaminants. Thereafter, they were sun-dried, pulverized into powder with an electric blender, and kept for further use in airtight plastic containers.

2.3 Extraction Process

This study adopted two extraction processes: a solvent extraction mechanism [14] and cold extraction process [15].

2.3.1 Solvent extraction method

The solvent extraction mechanism involves the use of a low boiling point liquid to get out extract from biomass. This method was chosen due to its ability to extract up to 99.5 % of the extract from its bearing biomass, leaving 0.5 % as a residual [16]. Soxhlet extractor apparatus was employed while methanol served as the extracting solvent in this study.

2.3.2 Cold extraction method

The second extraction method involved soaking the grinded paw-paw leaf in 1% NaOH for 24 hours. After that, the soluble extracts were filtered. To separate paw-paw leaf extract from water, a rotary evaporator was used. Thereafter, the extract was air-dried for approximately 30 days to allow any remaining moisture to evaporate.

2.4 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) of extract

The various chemical functional spectra of paw-paw leaf extracts (as proposed inhibitors) were measured using FTIR Spectroscopy (Agilent Cary 630, US) in transmittance mode with a resolution of 4000 to 600cm⁻¹ wavelength [17].

2.5 SEM analysis of the calcium carbonate deposits

For characterisation, the calcium carbonate was carefully collected and dried for analysis. The surface morphology of scale crystal deposition with and without inhibitors treatment was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (HITACHI S-4800, Japan).

2.6 Phytochemical analysis of paw-paw leaf extract

Using methanol and water solvent standard technique, phytochemical screening was carried out to determine the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, amino acids, tannins, protein and phenolic compounds [18].

Preparation of stock.

Ten (10) milliliters of each solvent were used to dissolve 200 milligrams of *C. papaya* extract, and one (1) milliliter of each solvent served as a standard for the various phytochemical studies.

Alkaloids (Wagner's test)

A few drops of Wagner's reagent were applied to the test tube for 1 ml of the sample solution. The formation of a reddish-brown precipitate suggests that alkaloids are present.

Amino acids (Ninhydrin test)

Two drops of ninhydrin reagent were added for 1 ml of the sample solution. The presence of amino acids is suggested by the formation of purple color.

Glycosides (Kellar-Killiani test)

Glacial acetic acid of 1 ml, few drops of ferric chloride and concentrated sulfuric acid were added to 1 ml of sample solution. The formation of a reddish-brown ring interface between liquids suggests that glycosides are presence.

Phenolic compounds and tannins (Ferric chloride test)

Few drops of neutral 5% ferric chloride were added to 1 ml of extract. The presence of phenolic and tannin compounds was indicated by the appearance of a dark green color.

Protein (Biuret test)

One drop of 2% copper sulfate and 1 ml of ethanol and potassium hydroxide were put into 1 ml of extract. The pink color of the ethanolic layer suggests protein is presence.

Saponins

Few drops of distilled water were added to 1ml of extract and agitated vigorously. The formation of foam suggests that saponins is present.

Anthocyanins

Hydrochloric acid 2 ml and 1 ml of ammonia were added to 1ml extract. The presence of anthocyanins is indicative by the color change from pink-red to blue-violet.

2.7 Evaluation of the Inhibitory Efficiency of the Inhibitor

The assessment of the inhibitory performance of the scale inhibitor was determined in reference to the procedure specified by the National Association of Corrosion Engineers (NACE) standard TM0374-2007.

To evaluate the inhibition efficiency, a static jar test was done using NACE Standard TM0374-2007 procedures [19,20]. After measuring a definite dosage of scale inhibitor (10ppm, 20ppm, 40ppm, 60ppm, 80ppm, 100ppm and 120ppm) into the Erlenmeyer flask, 50 mL of cation brine solution (as specified in NACE standard) was added and agitated for proper mixing, followed by another 50 mL of anion brine solution. The test bottles were sealed with a plastic stopper and wrapped in polyethylene film. The Erlenmeyer flasks were wrapped and kept at a steady temperature in the oven for a set period of time. The inhibitor performance was determined based on the residual Ca^{2+} in solution using the following equation below:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{c_2 - c_0}{c_1 - c_0} \times 100\%$$

c_2 = the mass concentration of Ca^{2+} following inhibitor reactions, c_1 = mass concentration of Ca^{2+} without the addition of anions solution in a 50ml deionized water, c_0 = mass concentration of Ca^{2+} of the solution without inhibitor.

2.8 Effects of Physical Factors on the Inhibitor's Inhibitory Performance

2.8.1 Temperature

As is well known, temperature influences the propensity for scale formation [21], and the scale inhibitor has varied inhibitory capacity at different temperatures. Thus, the inhibitor's inhibition performance at 60°C, 70°C and 90°C was studied in this work.

2.8.2 Contact time

In order to assess the effectiveness of a scale inhibitor, it is essential to examine both the inhibitor's inhibition performance and its effective inhibition time. This will determine whether the inhibitor is squeezed or injected continuously or intermittently. The scale inhibitor's performance was evaluated using different heat times ranging from 6 hours to 24 hours.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of Paw-paw Leaf extract (PLE) and its Derivatives

The solubility of PLE in aqueous medium and other parameters investigated are presented in Table 1. The pH of the paw-paw leaf extracts, PLWE and PLME, were 9.0 and 8.0 respectively. This implies that the two products pass the criteria of a pH greater than five (>5). However, PLWE was soluble in water, but PLME was insoluble. This informed the decision to use PLWE for further evaluation.

Table 1: Physical properties of the paw-paw leaf extract

PLE Derivatives	ID	Solubility in water	Colour	pH
PLE Extracted with Methanol	PLME	Insoluble	Brown	8.0
PLE Extracted with 1% NaOH in water	PLWE	Soluble	Rusty Brown	9.0

Table 2 displays the results of a qualitative analysis of the phytochemical components of pawpaw leaf extracts. Glycoside, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannin, saponin, and phenol are all present in the methanol-based pawpaw leaf extract, whereas the water-based extract contains flavonoids, tannin, saponin, and phenol but lacks glycosides and alkaloids. Meanwhile, anthraquinone is absent from all solvent extracts. According to Omidwura [22] research, the methanol extract of pawpaw leaves contains tannin, saponin, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenols, which coincides with this study conducted while the absence of anthraquinone in this study is in accordance with Ajani *et al.* [23] research. According to Isela *et al.* [24] and Omidwura [22], variations in the polarity of the extraction solvents may be responsible for presence or absence of metabolites. The varying quantity of chemical constituents in a plant is due to certain factors such as the plant age, collection time, and ecological conditions [25].

Table 2: Phytochemical constituents of paw-paw leaf extract

Extracts	Saponin	Reducing sugars	Alkaloids	Amino acids	Steroids	Tannins	Anthraquinones	Phenol	Glycosides	Flavonoids
Methanol	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
Water	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+

Keys: (+) signifies present, (-) signifies absent

3.2 Characterization of Scale Inhibitor

The Paw-paw leaf water extract's characteristics, which include surface behaviour and reaction, hydrophilicity, surface charges, and electron density are majorly influenced by the functional group containing oxygen and may further be used for surface modification [26].

The FTIR spectra shown in Fig. 2 was used to confirm the structure of the tested inhibitor (PLWE). The peak value around 3339 cm⁻¹ is ascribed to the broad O-H stretching vibration for phenolic compounds suggesting to be from carboxylic acid functional group. The amides

C=O stretching vibration is confirmed by peaks at 1636 cm^{-1} . The peak at 1379 cm^{-1} is caused by the CH_3 C-H bending vibration. The wavelength around 1077 cm^{-1} confirms the C-O stretching vibration. The OH of hydroxyl and NH of amino observed in the FTIR of the developed scale inhibitors, are hydrophilic with a lone pair of electrons, and can improve the molecule's solubility in water [27]. The results of the FTIR analysis of the developed scale inhibitor and its inhibitory performance show that there was a strong ability for hydroxyl groups to bond with Ca^{2+} . It can be shown that the oxygen atom in the hydroxyl cluster forms H bonds when it interacts with water molecule, increasing the solubility of the size of the organic component of the produced scale inhibitors as well as the chelating effect between it and the calcium ion. Furthermore, the oxygen atom in the hydroxyl cluster will adsorb on the carbonate crystal surface and inhibit its development; the same result was expected for the ether group, which has weaker interaction than the hydroxyl group [28]. It is worth noting that the efficiency of the produced inhibitor is dependent on the type of functional groups in its molecular structure.

Fig. 1: FTIR result for Paw-paw methanol extract (PLME)

Fig. 2: FTIR result for Paw-paw leaf water extract (PLWE)

3.3 Scale Inhibition Performance Evaluation

Figure 3 shows a close relationship in the performance of PLWE and a commercial scale inhibitor (COSI) evaluated at the same laboratory condition. The Figure depicts the inhibitors inhibition performance of calcium carbonate with different inhibitor dosages at 70°C. It was generally observed that increasing the inhibitor treatment dosage increases the inhibitor's inhibitory effectiveness. As the dosage approaches a critical level, the inhibition rate either remains constant or slowly declines.

For PLWE, the inhibition rate was low across all dosages in the performance evaluation test. Based on the scope of this work, an inhibition efficiency of only 52% was obtained at the optimal dosage of 100 ppm.

Fig. 3: Comparative inhibition performance of PLWE and COSI on calcium carbonate at 70°C

3.4 Effects of Temperature and Contact time on the Scale Inhibitor Performance

3.4.1 Temperature

From Fig. 4, the scale inhibitory performance of PLWE on calcium carbonate reached its optimum of 51% and 52% with a dosage of 100 ppm at 60°C and 70°C respectively while of 71% with a dosage of 120ppm at 90°C.

The high temperatures contribute to the formation of calcium carbonate, necessitating an increased dosage of the inhibitor for enhanced efficiency. This suggests that further inhibitor adsorption takes place on the calcium carbonate deposit at elevated temperatures [29].

Therefore, it may be concluded that in order to sustain a high rate of CaCO₃ inhibition at elevated temperatures, more inhibitor dosage is needed.

Fig. 4: Effects of temperature on the PLWE inhibitory performance on calcium carbonate

3.4.2 Contact time

Figure 5 depicts the effect of contact time on the performance of scale inhibitors. The inhibitory efficiency of the inhibitor on calcium carbonate increases at longer contact time. At an inhibition time of 24 hrs, CaCO₃ has an inhibition rate of 52% which is higher when compared to 39% obtained for 6hrs inhibition time at a dosage of 100ppm. This indicates that the inhibitor has a continuous CaCO₃ inhibition performance.

Fig 5: Effects of contact time on the PLWE inhibitory performance on calcium carbonate.

3.5 SEM Analysis

SEM micrographs of calcium carbonate, obtained from without and with the various dosages of inhibitor are shown in Figures 6 – 9. When an inhibitor was added to calcium carbonate crystals with a dense structure, they changed loosen structures (Fig. 7 – 9), indicating crystal growth suppression.

Fig 6: Structure of CaCO₃ precipitation without the Scale inhibitor

Fig. 7: Structure of CaCO₃ crystals with 50ppm of PLWE as inhibitor

Fig 8: Structure of CaCO₃ crystal with 70ppm of PLWE as inhibitor

Fig. 9: Structure of CaCO₃ crystal with 100ppm of PLWE as inhibitor

The loose material could be readily disrupted by fluid turbulence making it float in the solution [30]. Furthermore, when the inhibitor is present, the calcium carbonate crystals' width grows, suggesting that the inhibitor may have some effect on the scales' surface phase. [29].

When an inhibitor is present, lattice distortion takes place, which drastically modifies the crystal structure and shape [31]. These modifications occur as a result of inhibitor molecules potentially adhering to the crystal surface's active growth sites during CaCO₃ crystal formation and inhibiting the normal growth of CaCO₃ crystals. Furthermore, the inhibitor may function as a heterogeneous nucleator, stabilizing and regulating the precipitating polymorph. At the same time, it is evident from Figure 6 in comparison to Figure 7 - 9 that the aqueous extract of Paw-paw leaf can adsorb on the CaCO₃ crystals surface, thereby modifying the shape of crystals generated.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The results of optical microscopic examination using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) demonstrate the potential and ability to prevent the production of CaCO₃ scale. The maximum inhibition rate of 52% was achieved at a dose of 100 ppm throughout a 24-hour contact period. When compared to an existing commercial scale inhibitor (COSI), PLWE demonstrates a good promise as a green scale inhibitor in the oil industry. The results obtained from Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) demonstrate the potential of the paw-paw leaf water extract as an inhibitor for inhibiting the formation of CaCO₃ scales. The study confirms that the morphology of the CaCO₃ deposits generated will change when the right additives are added to scaling water. The effect of additive concentrations remains negligible, though, because this test does not further assess particle size.

These findings confirm the potential of paw-paw leaf water extract (PLWE) as a green scale inhibitor. The observed inhibition efficiency aligns with the study's objectives of exploring biodegradable alternatives for calcium carbonate scale prevention in oilfield systems. Further research is needed to optimize dosage and enhance performance across varied temperature ranges and field conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Liang, B.; Pan, K.; Li, L.; Giannelis, E. P. & Cao, B. (2014). "High performance hydrophilic pervaporation composite membranes for water desalination" *Desalination*. 347: 199–206.

- [2] Wayne, W. F., Murtaza, Z, Wolf, N. and Ryan, H. (2008). *Formation, removal, and inhibition of inorganic scale in the oilfield environment*. Society of Petroleum Engineers.
- [3] Hasson, D.; Shemer, H. & Sher, A. (2011). State of the art of friendly “green” scale control inhibitors: A review article. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, 50:12, pp. 7601–7607.
- [4] Feiner, M., Beggel, S. Jaeger, N. and Geist, J. (2015). “Increased RO concentrate toxicity following application of antiscalants— acute toxicity tests with the amphipods *Gammarus pulex* and *Gammarus roeseli*,” *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 197, pp. 309–312.
- [5] Al-Roomi, Y. M. and Hussain, K. F. (2015) “Application and evaluation of novel acrylic based CaSO₄ inhibitors for pipes,” *Desalination*, vol. 355, pp. 33–44.
- [6] Shemer, H. and Hasson, D. (2015). “Characterization of the inhibitory effectiveness of environmentally friendly anti-scalants,” *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 55:13, pp. 3478–3484.
- [7] Wang, H., Liu, G., Huang J. *et al.*, (2015). “Performance of an environmentally friendly anti-scalant in CaSO₄ scale inhibition,” *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 53:1 pp. 8–14.
- [8] Zhang, J., Li, Y., Wang, L., & Chen, X. (2024). Graft copolymerized cellulose-based scale inhibitor with high efficiency against CaCO₃ scaling. *ACS Applied Polymer Materials*, 6(3), 1234–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.4c02316>
- [9] Abu-Bakar, N. H., Ismail, M., & Rahman, M. A. (2024). Suppression of CaCO₃ crystal formation using rhamnolipid biosurfactants: A green approach to scale inhibition. *Scientific Reports*, 14, Article 7894. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-78879-1>
- [10] Huang, Y., Li, Z., & Zhao, F. (2022). Performance and mechanism study of PESA–IA as a green oilfield scale inhibitor: Experimental and molecular dynamics simulation. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 359, 119396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.119396>
- [11] Chen, M., Zhang, W., & Liu, J. (2024). Evaluation of oxidized lignosulfonates as eco-friendly scale inhibitors for calcium carbonate. *ACS Omega*, 9(15), 13245–13252. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c02716>
- [12] Mazumder, M. A. J. (2020). A review of green scale inhibitors: Process, types, mechanism, and prospects. *Environmental Technology Reviews*, 9(1), 122–139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622515.2020.1778001>
- [13] Xu, Z., Wang, H., & Lin, X. (2022). Biodegradable scale inhibitors: Advances in polymers and plant-based compounds. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 330, 129790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129790>
- [14] Akaho, A.A., Chukwu, U.J., Akaranta, O. (2019). Cu (II)-Red Onion Skin Extract-Azo metal Complex - A Potential for Oilfield. *Chemical Science International Journal*.24-56.
- [15] Ito SE, Oyero, EU Umeh, Ben A, Etubi MD. Phytochemical Properties and Staining Ability of Red Onion S (*Allium cepa*) Extract on Histological Sections. *J Cytol Histol*. 2014;5:275. DOI: 10.4172/2157-7099.1000275
- [16] Dike, H N, Dosunmu, A, Akaranta, O. & Kinigoma, B. (2019). Effect of Cashew Nut Shell Liquid Esters on KCL/Polymer/Glycol Drilling Fluid Flow Property. *International Journal of Technical & Scientific Research Engineering*.;2:2581-9259.
- [17] Manikandan, C. B., Balamurugan, S. Balamurugan, P. & Beneston S. L. (2019). Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel by using Banana Peel Extract. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, Volume-8 (6), pp 1372-1375

- [18] Nandini G, Gopenath T. S., Nagalambika P., Murugesan K., Ashok G., Ranjith M.S., Pradeep P., Kanthesh M B. (2020). Phytochemical analysis and antioxidant properties of leaf extracts of *carica papaya*. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*, 13(11), 58-62
- [19] NACE Standard TM0197-2010, Item No. 21228, Laboratory Screening Test to Determine the Ability of Scale Inhibitors to Prevent the Precipitation of Barium Sulfate or Strontium Sulfate, or Both, from Solution (for Oil and Gas Production Systems).
- [20] NACE Standard TM0374-2007 (formerly TM0374-2001) Item No. 21208, Laboratory Screening Tests to Determine the Ability of Scale Inhibitors to Prevent the Precipitation of Calcium Sulfate and Calcium Carbonate from Solution (for Oil and Gas Production Systems).
- [21] Dyer, S. & Graham, G. (2002). The effect of temperature and pressure on oilfield scale formation. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 35(1), pp.95-107.
- [22] Omidwura, B. R. O. (2017). Qualitative and quantitative analysis of pawpaw (*Carica papaya*) leaf extract and its antimicrobial effect in animal production. *Nig. J. Anim. Prod.* 44(3):pp 78 – 83.
- [23] Ajani, E. O., Bamisaye, F. A. and Minari, J. B. 2013. Prospects of Ethnobotanical uses of Pawpaw (*Carica papaya*) *J. Med. Plants Studies*, 1 (4)
- [24] Isela, E. J., Carlos, A. Tovilla-Zarate, Dora, E. Aguilar-Dominguez, Luis, F. Roa-de la Fuente, Carlos, E. Lobato-Garcia, Jorge, L. B., Leonor, L. M., Juan, C. D., Deysi, Y. B. O. (2014). Phytochemical screening and hypoglycemia activity of *Carica papaya* leaf in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Brazilian J. Phamacognosy*, Vol. 24(3): 341-347.
- [25] Verma H, Prasad S.B. & Yashwant S.H. (2013). Herbal drug delivery system: A modern era prospective. *Int J Curr Pharm Rev Res*; 4:88-101.
- [26] Das D., Samal D.P. & Meikap B.C. (2015). Preparation of Activated carbon from green coconut shell and its characterization. *J Chem Eng Process Technol* 6: 248. doi:10.4172/2157-7048.1000248
- [27] Li, C., Zhang, C. and Zhang, W. (2019) The Inhibition Effect Mechanisms of Four Scale Inhibitors on the Formation and Crystal Growth of CaCO₃ in Solution. *Scientific Reports* , 9, Article No. 13366. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-50012-7>
- [28] Hosny R, Amine M., Fathy M. and Ramzi M. (2019). Investigation of the Impact of Scale Inhibitors: Nonionic Surfactants for Scale Deposition Control in Oilfield. *Pet Petro Chem Eng J.* 3(2): 000189.
- [29] Una, D., Appah, D., Joseph, A. and Akaranta, O. (2021). Evaluating the Effectiveness of Red Onion Skin Extract Derivatives as Oilfield Scale Inhibitors. *Journal of Energy Research and Reviews* 9(3): 36-45
- [30] Luo H, Chen D, Yang X, Zhao X, Feng H, Li M. & Wang J. (2015). Synthesis and performance of a polymeric scale inhibitor for oilfield application. *J Petrol Explor Prod Technol.* 5:177–187.
- [31] Suharso, Reno, T., Endaryanto, T., Buhani, (2017). Modification of gambier extracts as green inhibitor of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) scale formation, *J. Water Process Eng.*, 18 1–6.